

Agro2Circular

D6.4 – Basis for future industrial implementation

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Authors: Salvador Navarro (GWC); Mari Carmen Cánovas (GWC); Sofía Martínez López (CTNC); José M. de la Torre Ramírez (DMC); Salvador García and María Nicolás (CETBIO); Fuensanta Monzó (CETEC) , Jaime Ortiz (CETEC); Víctor Fabregat (REGENERA)

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1 List of abbreviations

A2C Agro2Circular

met-PET Aluminium-metallised PET

Al Aluminium

PBAT Polybutylene adipate terephthalate

PHBV Polyhydroxybutyrate-co-valerate

PA Polyamide

PE Polyethylene

PET Polyethylene terephthalate

PP Polypropylene

LDPE Low-density polyethylene

LLDPE Linear low-density polyethylene

EVA Ethylene vinyl acetate

EVOH Ethylene vinyl alcohol

WP Work Package

D Deliverable

EG Ethylen glycol

TPA Terephthalic acid

F&V fruit and vegetable

UV Ultraviolet

DIS Data Integration System

2 Introduction

The A2C project aims to integrate and demonstrate innovative technologies at a pilot scale in southern Spain, laying the groundwork for their future industrial implementation. Through this project, various technologies have been developed and tested in real industrial environments, enabling the evaluation of their performance, the optimization of their operation, and the definition of effective strategies for the valorisation of by-products. Deliverables D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3 details the integration of the different technologies in 10 demonstrators including the validation of the resulting product by the end users and the Data Integration System (DIS).

As part of this process, efforts have been made to interconnect the different technologies involved, ensuring their compatibility and operational efficiency. This document presents these connections, with a particular focus on the input and output flows of each demonstrator, detailing the specific requirements of the materials that can be processed in each technological unit. Additionally, it includes the technical specifications necessary to ensure the quality and viability of the final products, aligning with the needs and demands of end users.

This analysis not only facilitates a comprehensive understanding of how the technologies function within the project but also lays the foundation for future industrial implementation, improvements and scalability of the processes, thus promoting the transition towards a more sustainable and innovative industrial model.

3 Executive summary

This document presents a protocol providing the essential information to be considered for the industrial implementation of the technologies involved in the DEMOs, with the goal of supporting stakeholders who consider to adopt and integrate these technologies into their operations. Because the technologies and processes are intellectual property protected and under an exploitation plan, the protocols will be extended and completed by the technology owners under licensing or commercial agreements.

The protocol covers the following aspects for each demonstrator:

- Process description including the description of the different steps, equipment involved, Process Flow Diagram (PFD) and Material Balance.
- Scaling factors
- Waste management
- Characteristics of the feedstock
- Description of the final product including potential applications by end users and market viability.

The document focuses on the interconnections and material flows between the different technologies, providing the technical information needed to ensure the quality and viability of the final products for end-users. The analysis helps lay the foundation for future industrial implementation and scalability of these processes.

Figure 1 illustrates the flowcharts and interactions between the 9 pilot scale demonstrators that have been built within the Agro2Circular project framework.

The A2C project involves 10 demonstrators that convert agri-food and plastic waste into various final products. Demonstrator 10 is a digital component that supports the traceability and scalability of the other nine demonstrators.

- **Demonstrator 1:** Upcycles multilayer/multimaterial plastic waste by separating layers and removing aluminium to get purer recycled plastic fractions. The process involves preliminary decontamination, optical sorting, delamination, and enzymatic

degradation to produce recycled plastic compounds, aluminium flakes, ethylene glycol (EG), and terephthalic acid (TPA).

- **Demonstrator 2:** Integrates fermentation technologies to upcycle PET monomers (EG and TPA) from Demonstrator 1 and lemon extract from Demonstrator 3 into ingredients for cosmetics, such as glycolic acid (GA), protocatechuic acid (PCA), and microbial oil.
- **Demonstrator 3:** Focuses on upcycling organic agri-food waste from lemons, artichokes, apples, and broccoli to recover antioxidant extracts and dietary fiber extracts through enzymatic extraction, purification, and stabilization. *
- **Demonstrator 4:** Extracts polyphenols and soluble dietary fibres from artichoke, lemon, and red grape waste using enzymatic and microwave-assisted extraction, followed by purification and stabilization methods like microencapsulation.
- **Demonstrator 5:** Demonstrates the bioprocess scalability of converting lemon waste from Demonstrator 3 into PHBV biodegradable plastic and carotenoids using a halophilic microorganism in a 300 L bioreactor.
- **Demonstrators 6 and 8:** Optimize blending and extrusion to produce biodegradable plastic compounds and films for food and agriculture, respectively, using PHBV from Demonstrator 5.
- **Demonstrators 7 and 9:** Recycle plastic waste streams from Demonstrator 1. Demo 7 uses non-metallized plastic for food packaging, while Demo 9 incorporates modified aluminium to create agricultural mulch with special optical properties

Demonstrator 10 complements the rest of the demonstrators as a powerful tool consisting of a central digital component aimed to support demos traceability and future industrial scalability and whose potential is explained in section 13.

Moreover, the study of the energy consumption of the technical demos at an economy of scale is presented in section 12.

Figure 1: Flowchart and interactions between demonstrators

Each demonstrator integrates different processes and steps based on different technologies with the aim of recycling two specific types of waste generated by the agri-food industry in the Region of Murcia: fruit and vegetable waste and multi-layer/multi-material plastic waste.

4 Demonstrator 1

4.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

4.1.1. Process description

Demonstrator 1 upcycles multilayer/multimaterial plastic waste by delaminating the different layers and removing the aluminium, obtaining fractions of recycled plastic fractions of higher purity.

Demonstrator 1 consists of the following stages:

- Step 1 Preliminary decontamination:** This is the first step of the demonstrator, performed at the GWC pilot plant. The shredded waste is transported by a conveyor (1) to a washing hopper (2) for intense agitation, then into a washing tank (3) where blades remove remaining waste. The material is then dried in a centrifuge (4) and transported to a cyclone before it reaches the optical sorter. The washing hopper uses permeate water from the treatment of wastewater from the washing tank. The process operates in approximately 10-minute cycles and can handle 5 to 6 kg per cycle, resulting in a line capacity of 30-35 kg/h. The objective of this step is to remove organic contamination and dirt.
- Step 1 Optical sorting:** The optical sorting system, developed by IRIS technology, uses an optical device to discriminate metallized fractions. The optical device is integrated to a conveyor and mechanical sorting able to separate the metallised fraction from the non metallised fraction with 80% efficiency. The metallised fraction goes to step 3 and the non-metallised fraction goes to Demonstrators 7 and 9
- Step 3: Delamination & Aluminium removal:** This technology has been developed by saperatec. The process uses a separation fluid with special additives that work at the interface, after delamination and washing, the material is separated, typically using a sink-float operation, polyethylene fraction goes to Demos 7 and 9, PE-PET fraction goes to step 4 and aluminium can be recovered in the form of flakes.
- Step 4 Enzymatic Degradation:** the objective of this step is to enzymatically recycle the PET/PE plastic waste fraction that cannot be mechanically recycled. The PET/PE fraction first undergoes a pre-treatment to reduce PET crystallinity, then is

enzymatically recycled in a bioreactor using a novel PETase enzyme to yield pure PE, terephthalic acid (TPA), and ethylene glycol (EG). The process requires a bioreactor with temperature and continuous pH control.

Figure 2 shows the process mass balance and Figure 3 the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 2 Process mass balance DEMO 1

Table 1: List of equipment DEMO 1

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Shredding machine	Bags and films shredding	1
Conveyor	Material transport	1
Washing Hopper	Initial agitation for decontamination	1
Washing Tank	Secondary cleaning and material transport	1
Centrifuge	Material drying	1
Cyclone	Ensures material is dry	1

Optical Equipment	Sorting	Discriminates metallized fractions	2
Delamination unit		Delamination and aluminium removal	3
Twin-screw extruder		Pre-treatment of PET/PE	4
Bioreactor		Enzymatic recycling of PET/PE	4
Filtration equipment		Separation of unreacted solid	4
Ultrafiltration system	(UF)	Water treatment	1

Figure 3 PFC DEMO 1

4.1.2. Scaling factors

Key aspects to consider in the Scaling-Up of Demonstrator 1:

- The preliminary decontamination is easily scalable by increasing the treatment capacity of the line

- Material feeding into the optical sorting system is a critical step. The fragment size and the speed of feeding on the conveyor belt directly impact the classifier's performance. Challenges like material overlap and dispersion on the conveyor belt must be considered for industrial scale-up to maintain performance.
- The delamination capacity is limited by the low bulk density of the multi-layer films, not the technology itself. The current maximum loading (4 kg per batch), could be increased in stationary units by optimizing the design based on the amount of material to process. Bulk density is a key factor
- The water from the washing line is treated by an ultrafiltration system to be reused in the process, which leaves a concentrated stream of pollutants/nutrients that can be used as a by-product.
- The scale-up of the enzymatic degradation demonstrated that the process for converting PET into EG and TPA can be successfully transferred from lab scale without a loss in performance. For commercial scale-up, the bioreactor volume would be the primary scaling factor, with process parameters like temperature, pH, and stirring speed maintained to ensure consistent conversion rates. Compounds released during hydrolysis can affect enzymatic activity if not properly managed.

4.1.3. Waste management

Water Treatment: The ultrafiltration system with a permeate production capacity of 800 L/h was more than sufficient for the demonstration's water volume (2000 L treated). The design and capacity of this system can be scaled linearly with the overall water volume of a full-scale industrial washing line.

Delamination Fluid: The separation fluid used in the delamination process is not consumed and can be purified and recycled.

Washing Water Concentrate: The concentrated wastewater (retentate from ultrafiltration) contains a high concentration of organic compounds and sugars. This stream, which would otherwise be a waste, can be reused as a carbon source for the bioproduction of PHBV in Demonstrator 5. The water composition would need to be tested and potentially mixed with an artificial solution for a large industrial operation.

Unreacted Solids (from enzymatic recycling): The remaining solids after enzymatic degradation, composed of highly crystalline PET and non-enzyme-attacked PE, can be

separated by simple flotation. The recovered PE can be reused as a pure material, while the unreacted PET is returned to the pre-treatment stage

Non-hazardous Filter Residues: Filter residues from the water treatment system are classified as non-hazardous and can be thermally utilized.

4.2 Classification and Characteristics of the feedstock (waste or material coming from other Demos)

The containers of multilayer aseptic bags are mixed waste originating from the industrial activity of the food sector. They are not classified as hazardous waste based on their origin and composition, therefore, they should be managed as non-hazardous waste.

Table 2 DEMO 1 FEEDSTOCK CLASSIFICATION

WASTE	LER CODE	DESCRIPTION
Multilayer aseptic bag packaging	15 01 06	Mixed packaging [including packaging waste from municipal selective collection]

To help with the waste management, this feedstock is identified and gathered in DEMO 10, the Data Integration System thanks to the mobile app, the blockchain service and the core cloud app. Link 1 shows the identification of the waste that was sent from MOCITOS to GWC. Link 2 generates the report for printing and signing.

Table 3 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (Multilayer aseptic bag packaging)

MULTILAYER ASEPTIC BAG PACKAGING
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It must contain aluminium. -Waste must be pre-conditioned before storage. The cap should be removed, and the rest of the material should be cleaned before storage in order to eliminate impurities and organic matter, which could cause issues in subsequent treatments due to the high glucose content. -The waste should be stored in appropriate drums or containers, using protective and sealed covers to prevent external contamination. -Properly labelled waste.

-The waste must come from exclusive food use and be processed optimally throughout the entire process to continue its path in the food sector.

Agricultural mulch waste comes from the activities of the primary sector. They are not classified as hazardous waste due to their composition and origin; therefore, they should be managed as non-hazardous waste.

Table 4 DEMO 9 FEEDSTOCK CLASSIFICATION. Agricultural mulch

WASTE	LER CODE	DESCRIPTION
Agricultural mulch.	02 01 04	Waste from agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting, and fishing. Plastic waste

Table 5 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (Agricultural disinfection film)

Agricultural disinfection film
The most common base material for agricultural disinfection films is polyethylene (PE), especially high-density polyethylene (HDPE) or low-density polyethylene (LDPE). Multilayer composition.

4.3 Description of Final Products Obtained

4.3.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

PRODUCT	COMPOSITION	Characteristics
LDPE-EVOH-PA flakes	LDPE>95%	Extrusion grade
LDPE flakes	LDPE>95%	Extrusion grade
Aluminium flakes	Al> 95% Allowed materials (Layer structure): P1/Alu/P2	Flake size: >50mm: Below 5% <5mm: Below 10%

	<p>P1/Alu/P1/P3 P1 monofoil P3 monofoil</p> <p>Where P1 is PE Where P2 is either PE or PET Where P3 is PET Where Alu is either metallised or foil</p>	<p>Contamination (eg. other polymers than PE, PET; glass; dirt; organics; metal): max. 1% Throughput: 2...10% per batch, depending on bulk weight of the feedstock</p>
Ethylene glycol	3g EG/l aqueous solution	
Terephthalic acid	TPA > 95% / 21g TPA/1L aqueous solution	

Both LDPE-EVOH-PA pellets and aluminium flakes are included as products in DEMO 10 in order to track feedstock transformation processes into products. Link 3 shows the traceability of a determined plastic lot in the shape of pellets for further compounding.

4.3.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

PRODUCT	Potential application
LDPE flakes	Flexible packaging (DEMO 7) Agricultural films (DEMO 9)
Aluminium flakes	Filler for plastic composite Agricultural films (DEMO 9) Metallised pigment effect
Ethylene glycol	Bioproduction of Ethylene Glycol PET polymerisation
Terephthalic acid	Bioproduction of protocatechuic acid PET polymerisation

Link 4 shows the Digital Product Passport of a potential agricultural mulch film traced on Data Integration System.

In Demonstrator 1, various products and by-products are obtained, such as LDPE-EVOH-PA flakes, which are further used in Demonstrator 7. Other final products from Demonstrator 1 are integrated into different demonstrators described later: aluminium flakes in Demonstrator 9, and ethylene glycol (EG) and terephthalic acid (TA) in Demonstrator 2

5 Demonstrator 2

5.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

5.1.1 Process description

Demonstrator 2 integrates three fermentation technologies, developed by UNIMIB to upcycle PET monomers (ethylene glycol-EG and terephthalic acid-TPA) from DEMO 1 and lemon extract (LE) from DEMO 3. The aim is to produce valuable ingredients for the cosmetic industry: glycolic acid (GA), protocatechuic acid (PCA), and microbial oil.

- 1 Step 1 Bioconversion of Ethylene Glycol (EG) to Glycolic Acid (GA):** This is a two-step fermentation process using the yeast *Scheffersomyces stipitis* in a 30L bioreactor. The first phase is a growth phase where biomass is expanded in a medium containing yeast extract, and glucose. The second phase begins after glucose is exhausted, with the addition of a fresh media containing yeast extract, and EG, which results in GA production. The process is maintained at controlled pH and temperature.
- 2 Step 2 Bioconversion of Terephthalic Acid (TPA) to Protocatechuic Acid (PCA):** This is a fed-batch fermentation process using an engineered bacterium, *P. putida* in a 2L bioreactor. TPA is added to the feed medium along with glucose, and other nutrients. The bioreactor is maintained at controlled pH and temperature. The PCA is then extracted from the medium, followed by acid precipitation and lyophilization to yield a powder containing PCA.
- 3 Step 3 Microbial Oil Production from Lemon Extract (LE):** This is a batch fermentation process using the oleaginous yeast *Cutaneotrichosporon oleaginosus* in a 2L bioreactor. The lemon extract serves as a complete medium with a C/N ratio of 80, which is ideal for oil accumulation. The process is successful in achieving a 50% lipid content in the biomass without the addition of extra nutrients. The extracted oil is recovered using an environmentally friendly solvent mixture, as an alternative to the traditional, toxic Folch method.

Figure 4 shows the process mass balance and Figure 5 the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 4 Process mass balance DEMO 2

Figure 5 PFC DEMO 2

Table 6: List of equipment DEMO 2

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Bioreactor	EG bioconversion into GA	1
Bioreactor	TPA bioconversion into PCA	2
Bioreactor	Microbial oil production from lemon extract	3
Rotavapor apparatus	Used for recovering solvent	2,3
Lyophilization process	Used to dehydrate the final PCA product	2
Centrifuge	Used for separating cell pellets and purifying samples	1,2,3

5.1.2 Scaling factors

Key aspects to consider in the Scaling-Up of Demonstrator 2:

- EG to GA: The bioconversion process was successfully scaled up from a 2L laboratory bioreactor at UNIMIB to a 30L bioreactor at CETEC without a loss in performance, demonstrating its robustness.
- TPA to PCA: The process was demonstrated on a 2L bioreactor scale. The main challenges were TPA solubility and uptake, with a final conversion rate of 31%. Further optimization of the C/N ratio, trace elements, aeration, and agitation is needed to enhance PCA accumulation for a successful scale-up.
- The process successfully produced microbial oil from lemon extract. The demonstration achieved a 50% lipid content in the biomass within 48 hours.
- Extracts used as substrates (e.g. lemon extract from Demo 3, or EG/TPA from Demo 1) must be sufficiently purified to avoid toxicity or inhibition of microbial growth. Impurities can severely impact yeast viability and fermentation efficiency.
- As the processes scale beyond 30 L, precise control of key parameters (pH, temperature, oxygen transfer, agitation) becomes increasingly critical to maintain product yields and reproducibility.
- Waste-derived inputs may vary significantly in composition depending on origin and batch. This variability requires prior validation and potentially pre-standardization to ensure process stability and consistent bioconversion results.

5.1.3 Waste management

TPA Bioconversion By-products: After the extraction of PCA, the remaining liquid is a supernatant that can be reused in the next fermentation.

Microbial Oil Production By-products: The process uses lemon extract as a feedstock, which is already a waste stream. The oil extraction process utilizes green solvents as a substitute for traditional toxic solvents, thereby minimizing the environmental impact of the extraction procedure

5.2 Classification and Characteristics of the feedstock (waste or material coming from other Demos)

Table 7 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (fruit waste)

Fruit waste
-High sugary fruit waste
-Liquid

5.3 Description of Final Products Obtained

5.3.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

Product	Active principle
Fermentation broth (1)	18 g/L glycolic acid
Protocatechuic acid (2)	PCA power and NH ₄ CL 12% w/w (ACR)
Microbial oils (3)	OIL from LE (<i>C. oleaginosa</i>) gran (OMC)

5.3.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

The final products have potential application as an ingredient for cosmetic formulations, as it has been demonstrated by the end-user within the frame work of the project.

Product	Composition
Skin lightening cream	5% active principle (1)
Skin moisturising cream	5% principle (2)
Skin moisturising cream	5% active principle (3)

Lolo Cosmetic tested the 3 products, two formulas moisturising skin cream were prepared with the active ingredient (Protocatechuic acid - and OIL from *C. oleaginosa* at 5% and one formula of lightening skin cream with the active ingredient (Glycolic Acid 18g/L) at 5%.

Figure 6: Cosmetic formulations

The tests carried out to evaluate the moisturising effect confirmed an increase of the CUTANEOUS HYDRATION by 36.70% Protocatechuic acid and 22.19 microbial oil. This CUTANEOUS HYDRATION occurs in all two cases, i.e. with the three extracts tested, from the first hour onwards.

6 Demonstrator 3

6.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

6.1.1 Process description

Demonstrator 3, located at the CTNC's pilot plant, focuses on upcycling organic agri-food waste (from lemon, artichoke, apple, and broccoli). The process aims to recover antioxidant extracts rich in polyphenols and dietary fibre extracts. The technologies involved—enzymatic extraction, purification, and stabilization—were previously optimized at a laboratory scale and are now integrated at a pilot scale. The pilot plant is designed to process 100 kg/h of waste and has achieved a total extract production of more than 15 kg

The process is divided into three main stages: extraction, purification, and stabilization.

- Step 1 Pre-treatment and Enzymatic Extraction:** The process begins with pre-treatment, where waste is crushed using an industrial cutter to reduce particle size and homogenize the material. The pre-treated material is then subjected to enzymatic extraction (EAE) in a double-jacketed mixing tank. The optimized conditions for this stage include a solid-to-water ratio, temperature and treatment time. After the enzymatic extraction, the mixture is heated to deactivate the enzyme.
- Step 2 Phase Separation and Purification:** the liquid and solid phases are separated and the target compounds purify from each. The heated mixture is cooled and separated into a solid phase and a liquid phase using a decanter. The liquid phase, rich in phenolic compounds, is first concentrated using a filtration plant. It is then purified using an adsorption-desorption process. The solid phase, which contains fibre, is purified through a bleaching process with an oxidizing agent. This is followed by a final washing with water by showering
- Step 3 Stabilization:** The stabilisation of the final extracts increases their shelf life and facilitates handling. The liquid extract, rich in phenolic compounds, has the solvent evaporated in a rotary evaporator. The resulting extract is then dehydrated by freeze-

drying to produce a powder. The purified solid fibre extract is dehydrated using a hot air convection chamber.

Figure 7 shows the process mass balance and Figure 8 the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 7 Process mass balance DEMO 3

Figure 8 PFC DEMO 3

Table 8: List of equipment DEMO 3

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Industrial Cutter	Used for the pre-treatment of the agri-food waste	1
Double-Jacketed Mixing Tank	Used for enzymatic extraction and enzyme inhibition by heating.	1
Decanter:	used to separate the solid and liquid phases	2
Pilot Filtration Plant	Used for concentrating the liquid phase before resin adsorption	2

Adsorption/Desorption Plant	For purifying phenolic compounds using polymeric resins.	2
Rotary Evaporator:	Evaporates the solvent from the purified phenolic extract	2
Freeze-Dryer	Dehydrates the liquid extract to a powder.	3
Hot Air Convection Chamber	Dehydrates the purified solid fiber extract	3
Industrial Steam Kettle	Concentrates the sugar-rich liquid fraction for other demonstrators.	1

6.1.2 Scaling factors

Key aspects to consider in the Scaling-Up of Demonstrator 3:

- Stabilization (Bottleneck): The stabilization stage, particularly freeze-drying (lyophilization), was identified as a major bottleneck due to the low processing capacity of 1-2 kg/day compared to the extraction rate of 200 L/h and purification rate of at least 50 L/h. This stage is also highly energy-intensive and is recommended to be skipped if the extracts can be used directly by end-users.
- Training in biotechnological processes and quality control.
- Quality control: Testing for polyphenol content, fibre, moisture, stability.
- Evaluate sanitary and industrial safety requirements for the use of extracts in food/cosmetics.
- Due to the high variability of raw materials, a pretreatment is needed to homogenize.
- Microbiological stability, polyphenol or fibre content.

6.1.3 Waste management

Non-useful fractions (seeds, hard shells): must have a secondary valorization route: composting, biomass, animal feed.

Wastewater: The purification of fibre generates significant wastewater from the washing process. Optimization efforts led to a 34.7% reduction in water consumption by reusing water from the first washes, reducing the total water consumed from 357.6 L to 233.6 L per 50 kg batch of waste processed. A counter-current washing system was also studied as a potential solution for further water optimization. Osmotised or treated network water, reusable after filtration.

Solvent: The solvent used in the resin desorption process is a by-product that can be recovered by distillation and reused in the process, reducing chemical waste.

Sugar-Rich Permeate: The liquid fraction that permeates after the resin adsorption step is rich in sugars and other organic compounds. This stream is concentrated and sent to other demonstrators (DEMO 2 and 5) to be used as a substrate for fermentation processes, specifically for producing PBHV and microbial essential oils. This action valorises a potential waste stream into a valuable resource for other processes

6.2 Classification and Characteristics of the feedstock (waste or material coming from other Demos)

Table 9 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (Fruit & vegetable waste)

Fruit & vegetable waste
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate microbiological quality (low microbiological load and absence of pathogens) - F&V waste not fermented or decomposed (to avoid generation of undesirable compounds that alter the composition) - Absence of chemical contaminants (avoid presence of pesticides, heavy metals, etc.). - Favourable composition. In particular: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of antioxidant compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids), <p>High fibre content.</p>

DEMO 10 also holds organic waste management, which begins with the identification of the lemon waste.

6.3 Description of Final Products Obtained

6.3.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

Product	Composition
Liquid extract reach in sugar	Sugar (about 5 % sugars by wet weight \equiv > 30 % by dry weight)
Phenolic extract (1)	Moulds and yeasts, <i>E. coli</i> and mesophilic aerobes <10 cfu/g Absence of pathogens (Salmonella and Listeria) Pesticides <0.01 mg/kg Heavy metals <0.05 mg/kg Phenolic compounds content \geq 15 % (dry weight)
Fibre extract (2)	Moulds and yeasts, <i>E. coli</i> and mesophilic aerobes <10 cfu/g Absence of pathogens (Salmonella and Listeria) Pesticides <0.01 mg/kg Heavy metals <0.05 mg/kg Fibre content \geq 70 % (dry weight)

All subproducts are gathered in DEMO 10, both liquid extract reach in sugars for DEMO 5 and extracts for final products formulations. Link 5 shows the traceability of the fiber extract obtained from the lemon waste.

6.3.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

Product	Active principle
Food formulations	<u>Phenolic extract:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Functional foods - Natural antioxidant - Dietary supplements <u>Fibre extract:</u>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Functional foods - Prebiotics - Dietary supplements - Thickener
Cosmetic formulations	<p><u>Phenolic extract:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Antioxidant for the skin - Anti-aging creams <p><u>Fibre extract:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used as a thickening and texturizing agent - Used as a natural exfoliant

6.1.2.1. Food formulations

During the implementation of the A2C project, the phenolic and fibre extracts obtained in DEMO 3 have been used by food companies for the development of new food formulations at pilot scale (formulations previously optimised at laboratory scale).

Specifically, the following formulations have been developed:

MCT Formulations

Based on the results obtained in the laboratory-scale food formulation, Agrotransformados (MCT) has manufactured:

- o Apple compote with broccoli phenolic extract (production of 3000 kg)
- o Strawberry jam with apple fibre (production of 3000 kg)
- o Orange juice with phenolic lemon extract (production of 6000 kg)

Figure 9 Manufacture of strawberry jam with apple fibre

Figure 10 . Manufacture of orange juice with phenolic lemon extract

ALM Formulations

Based on the results obtained in the laboratory-scale food formulation, Laboratorios Almond (ALM) has manufactured:

- Vegetable dessert with apple fibre (production of 1500 kg)
- Vegan hamburger powder with lemon fibre (production of 300 kg)
- Vegan hamburger powder with artichoke fibre (production of 300 kg)

Figure 11 Manufacture of vegetable dessert with apple fibre at ALM facilities

CITRO Formulations

Based on the results obtained in the laboratory-scale food formulation, Citromil (CITRO) has manufactured:

- Lemon juice with lemon fibre (production of 3000 kg)
- Lemon juice with phenolic lemon extract (production of 3000 kg)

Figure 12 Lemon juice production at CITRO facilities

7 Demonstrator 4

7.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

7.1.1 Process description

This section describes the pilot-scale implementation of Route 2 for the upcycling of agri-food waste at the DMC facilities in Alhendín, Spain. The process focuses on extracting polyphenols and soluble dietary fibers from artichoke stems and leaves, lemon peels, and grape pomace. Demonstrator 4, as a pilot plant, integrates several technologies including pre-treatment, enzymatic-assisted extraction (EAE), microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), ultra-filtration, and resin purification. The goal is to obtain high-purity extracts for use in food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic formulations.

The process for Route 2 is a multi-step operation with a dual-phase output:

- 1 Step 1 Pre-treatment and Enzymatic Extraction (EAE):** This step prepares the agri-food waste for extraction and recovers soluble dietary fibers and some polyphenols. The process begins with crushing the waste using an industrial cutter to reduce particle size. This pre-treatment homogenizes the raw material and increases the surface area for the subsequent enzymatic attack. The crushed waste is then treated with an enzyme at an optimised temperature, treatment time, solid-to-water ratio and pH. After this treatment, the mixture is sieved to separate it into a solid fraction and a liquid fraction.
- 2 Step 2 Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE):** The remaining polyphenols from the solid fraction are extracted after the enzymatic treatment. The solid residue from the EAE step is subjected to MAE using a custom-built SAIREM microwave extractor. The extraction is performed with a hydroalcoholic solution at optimised solid-to-extractant ratio, temperature, treatment time and microwave power. This heats the water within the cells, increasing pressure and breaking the cell walls, causing polyphenols to leak into the solvent. The liquid hydroalcoholic solution is then separated from the solid waste by filtration.

3 **Step 3 Purification and Stabilization:** the extracts are purified and prepared for final use. This stage involves purifying the liquid fractions obtained from both the EAE and MAE processes:

- **Ultra-filtration:** The liquid fraction from EAE is purified using an ultrafiltration plant. This separates soluble fibers from polyphenols, which are then further purified. The fiber-enriched solution is dried in a convection oven to obtain a powder with 45-70% fiber content.
- **Resin Purification:** The polyphenol-rich fractions from both the ultra-filtration and MAE are combined and purified using resins. This resin selectively adsorbs polyphenols. After adsorption, the polyphenols are eluted with ethanol. The purified extract has a polyphenol concentration of around 70%.
- **Microencapsulation:** For enhanced shelf-life and stability, the purified polyphenol extracts can be microencapsulated into alginate beads, which are then used in nutraceutical and cosmetic formulations.

Figure 13 shows the process mass balance and Figure 14 the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 13 Process mass balance DEMO 4

Figure 14 PFC DEMO 4

Table 10: List of equipment DEMO 3

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Industrial Cutter	For waste pre-treatment	1
Microwave Extractor	Used for extraction	2
Ultrafiltration Plant	used to separate the solid and liquid phases	3
Resin Purification Column	For purifying phenolic compounds	3
Convection Oven	For drying fibre extracts	3
Freeze-dryer (Lyophilization)::	An alternative stabilization method for extracts	3

7.1.2 Scaling factors

- Purification: Resin purification is identified as a bottleneck due to the large quantities of resin required and the time-consuming nature of the process.
- Key aspects to consider in the Scaling-Up of Demonstrator 4:
- Stabilization: The process uses dehydration in a convection oven instead of lyophilization (freeze-drying) to reduce energy consumption. Lyophilization is very energy-intensive and is considered a bottleneck.
- Training in biotechnological processes and quality control.
- Quality control: Testing for polyphenol content, fibre, moisture, stability.
- Evaluate sanitary and industrial safety requirements for the use of extracts in food/cosmetics.
- Due to the high variability of raw materials, a pretreatment is needed to homogenize.
- Microbiological stability, polyphenol or fibre content.

7.1.3 Waste management

Non-useful fractions (seeds, hard shells) must have a secondary valorisation route: composting, biomass, animal feed.

MAE Solid Waste: The solid part remaining after microwave-assisted extraction (mainly the cellulosic part) can be used as a nutrient source for microorganisms in other demonstrators, specifically DEMO 5. This converts a waste stream into a valuable feedstock.

Purification By-products: The ethanol used for resin desorption can be recovered by distillation and reused in the process. This helps to minimize chemical waste. The resin itself is also reused, although its reusability is a time-consuming step.

Water Consumption: While water is not recovered in this process, efforts can be made to optimize water consumption by reducing the proportion of the oxidizing agent and reusing wash water, as was studied in the parallel DEMO 3

7.2 Classification and Characteristics of the feedstock (waste or material coming from other Demos)

Table 11 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (Fruit & vegetable waste)

Fruit & vegetable waste
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate microbiological quality (low microbiological load and absence of pathogens) - F&V waste not fermented or decomposed (to avoid generation of undesirable compounds that alter the composition) - Absence of chemical contaminants (avoid presence of pesticides, heavy metals, etc.). - Favourable composition. In particular: Presence of antioxidant compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids),

DEMO 10 includes the artichoke waste identification, which was used as DEMO 4 feedstock. Link 6 shows the identification of the waste in the DIS platform.

7.3 Description of Final Products Obtained

7.3.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

Product	Composition
Antioxidant extract (1)	Moulds and yeasts, <i>E. coli</i> and mesophilic aerobes <10 cfu/g Absence of pathogens (Salmonella and Listeria) Pesticides <0.01 mg/kg Heavy metals <0.05 mg/kg <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Artichoke extract: > 40 % polyphenols content - Grape extract: > 60 % polyphenols content
Fibre extract (2)	Moulds and yeasts, <i>E. coli</i> and mesophilic aerobes <10 cfu/g

	<p>Absence of pathogens (Salmonella and Listeria)</p> <p>Pesticides <0.01 mg/kg</p> <p>Heavy metals <0.05 mg/kg</p> <p>Fibre content ≥ 70 % (dry weight)</p>
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Both antioxidant and fibre extracts are included in DEMO 10 for testing their integration in final nutraceutical products. Link 7 shows the grape extract characterization and traceability that is used in the nutraceutical product.

7.3.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

7.3.2.1 Nutraceutical formulations

With the polyphenol extract in solid form (microcapsules or solid powder) the nutraceutical is prepared adding excipients and other food complements that increase, even more, the added value of these products.

Among the excipients used, Citrate Zinc and microcrystalline cellulose are included.

The reference used for the formulation is the commercial product AlioCare®, made of allium extracts with ascorbic acid. The A2C nutraceutical formulation substituted the ascorbic acid in the formula by the antioxidant extracts obtained. The most promising extracts were artichoke and grapes, so two formulas have been developed, one for each extract. Also, the microencapsulated grape extract has been used looking for a more stable formulation.

These nutraceuticals are presented in hydroxypropyl methylcellulose capsules, each containing 500 mg of the nutraceutical preparation. The capsules are specifically designed to ensure the proper release of the solid contents while protecting the consumer from unpleasant flavours, particularly bitterness, during intake.

The amount of antioxidant extract in each capsule are 200 mg for artichoke and 140 mg for red grape, which corresponds with the standard amount of polyphenols present in other nutraceuticals present in the market.

Starting from 1000 L of liquid extract (artichoke and grape), approximately 500 gr - 1000 gr of each extract with the expected specification (described in D4.4) are obtained. With 500 grams of antioxidant extract, 1.5 kg of artichoke nutraceutical powder formulations have

been prepared (CynaraCare), and 2 kg of nutraceuticals with encapsulated red grape extract (VitiCare).

*Figure 15 Nutraceutical based on artichoke extract (left).
Nutraceutical based on Red grape extract (right)*

Each capsule contains 500 mg of the powder formulations with 100 mg of polyphenols. More than 3000 capsules of each type of nutraceutical were prepared. The capsules were packed in bottles of 30 units per bottle.

These nutraceutical products are also included in DEMO 10. Thanks to all technologies gathered on DIS, it has been able to generate a final Digital Product Passport which identifies each individual bottle with all the traceability and characterization of the containing product. (Link 8).

7.3.2.2 Cosmetic formulations

Using 4 of the extracts obtained in DEMO 4 (lemon polyphenols and aqueous and artichoke polyphenols with and without microencapsulation (beads)), Lolo prepared 4 emulsions with each active ingredient at 5% of the active ingredients with the following compositions

The formulas were tested in terms of both sensitivity and specificity, and it was found that skin hydration increases in all the extracts tested, being the artichoke extracts the most promising ones. The encapsulated extracts perform better than their non-encapsulated equivalents.

8 Demonstrator 5

8.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

8.1.1 Process description

Demonstrator 5 aims to demonstrate the scalability of a bioprocess that upcycles lemon waste from DEMO 3 into PHBV biodegradable plastic and carotenoids. The process uses a halophilic microorganism, which can grow in high salt concentrations, reducing the need for sterile conditions and allowing for co-production of both PHBV and carotenoids. The production is scaled up to a 300 L bioreactor.

The process consists of three main stages: biomass production, PHBV extraction, and carotenoid recovery.

Step 1 Biomass Production (Fermentation, Filtration, and Drying): PHBV-rich biomass is produced using lemon waste as a carbon source. The fermentation is performed at optimising temperature, nutrient ratio, concentration of salt, agitation and aeration. After fermentation, the PHBV-rich biomass is concentrated using tangential filtration, then, the concentrated biomass is then added to a pressure-reduced evaporator to remove water at low temperature. Finally, the biomass is dried in an oven.

Step 2 PHBV Extraction: High-purity PHBV is recovered from the dried biomass. This step is carried out using a "greener" solvent in a 1 L extraction pressure vessel. The dried biomass is loaded into the vessel with solvent and heated at optimised temperature and residence time. This dissolves the PHBV and carotenoids, which are then discharged and cooled to form a solvent-rich gel. Excess solvent is removed from the gel using a custom filter, carotenoids remain in the solvent and the PHBV pelletised

Figure 17 shows the process mass balance and Figure 17 the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 16 Process mass balance DEMO 5

Figure 17 PFC DEMO 5

Table 12: List of equipment DEMO 5

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Bioreactors	fermentation	1
Tangential Filtration Unit	Used for concentrating the biomass and removing brine	1
Evaporator Machine	Removes water from the concentrated culture and brine by reducing pressure	1
Oven:	Dries the biomass	1
Extraction Pressure Vessel	Used for PHBV extraction	2
Filter Press	Separates excess solvent from the PHBV gel	2
Electrodialysis Stack:	A pilot system for salt recovery from the brine.	1
Extruder	Used to pelletize the dry PHBV polymer	2

8.1.2 Scaling factors

Biomass Fermentation: The fermentation process was successfully scaled up to 300 L, which is a significant achievement from laboratory-scale studies without a loss in performance, demonstrating its robustness. It requires a balance between cost, fermentation time, and yield, especially under non-sterile conditions.

PHBV Extraction: The extraction process, developed at a 10 L pilot scale at WETSUS, was successfully replicated in a 1 L demonstrator unit, proving its principles are scalable. A key challenge for upscaling is to maintain a high-quality biomass with high thermal stability and a low content of unwanted solids to ensure efficient extraction.

Waste Streams: The process successfully used agri-food waste (lemon extract) as a feedstock, replacing commercial sugars and demonstrating a circular economy approach.

By-product Recovery: Technologies for recovering salts via electrodialysis and carotenoids from the extraction solvent have been developed at a lab scale and will be further tested in DEMO 5 at a pilot level.

8.1.3 Waste management

Carotenoids recovery: The filtrate from the PHBV extraction, which is characteristically orange due to carotenoids content, can be further concentrated or purified for carotenoids recovery and characterization. A separate system involving electrodialysis is used to recover salts from the brine produced during tangential filtration.

Brine and salt recovery: This brine is not a waste but a resource. Electrodialysis is used to recover the salts for reuse in new fermentation batches, thereby reducing waste and costs. The water from the biomass concentration is also evaporated and condensed, and the dry salts are collected to be reused in new fermentation batches

The solid biomass remaining after PHBV extraction is considered a by-product. The quality of these solids can be improved through a mild SDS washing step, which removes soluble organic and inorganic matter. The remaining solids can be potentially valorised, using it as a nutrient in the fermentation

Contaminated Solvent: The solvent used for PHBV extraction can be contaminated with non-PHA materials from the biomass. This "dirty" solvent is recovered through distillation and gel extrusion, which allows for its reuse in subsequent extraction cycles. An overall solvent recovery efficiency of about 75% was achieved.

8.2 Classification and Characteristics of the feedstock (waste or material coming from other Demos)

Table 13 WASTE REQUIREMENTS (Fruit waste)

Fruit waste
<p>In the A2C project, the optimal fruit waste for the fermentative process aimed at obtaining PHBV and carotenoids had a total sugar concentration of 90 g/L. While any fruit waste with a high sugar concentration can be used as a carbon source, in Demo 5, lemon waste was the most suitable after also evaluating apple and grape waste. The high sugar concentration and its high availability in the liquid medium contributed to a significant yield in PHBV production. These residues were diluted in the culture medium to reach a final sugar concentration of 10 g/L at the start of fermentation. To meet these requirements, the liquid lemon residue was added at 14% (v/v). Since the lemon residue is in a liquid state, it is essential that the waste used has been previously treated to ensure its liquid form, facilitating mixing and sugar availability in the fermentation medium.</p>

Lemon extract subproduct is also included in DEMO 10, bringing the possibility of identifying the feedstock used for the PHBV production.

8.3 Description of Final Products Obtained

8.3.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

Product	Composition	Properties
PHBV Biodegradable plastic	3-Hydroxy valerate (3-HV) content (%)= 27	Melting point (°C)= 143 Tensile Strength (MPa)= 14 Elongation at Break (%)= 26

PHBV as product is also included in DEMO 10, which will potentially be included in biodegradable plastic formulations.

8.3.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

Product	Composition	Properties
Formulations for packaging (DEMO6)	PHBV-PBAT	Biodegradable in soil and water Tensile strength >25 MPa Tensile strain >450 %
Formulations for agricultural films (DEMO 8)	PHBV- Starch PAT	Biodegradable in soil and water Tensile strength >25 MPa Tensile strain >450 %

9 DEMONSTRATORS 6 and 8

9.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

9.1.1 Process description

Demonstrators 6 and 8 focus on optimizing the blending and extrusion processes to produce biodegradable plastic compounds and films for the food (Demo 6) and agricultural (Demo 8) sectors, using the PHBV obtained from Demonstrator 5.

The process involves:

- 1 Step 1: dosing biodegradable resins gravimetrically
- 2 Step 2: mixing in a BANBURY® MIXER
- 3 Step 3: discharged into a transport conveyor
- 4 Step 4: extruder for granulation

The material produced in Demonstrator 5 (PHBV) needs to be dried before this blending step, and the resulting blends must also be pre-dried to prevent the formation of gels or foaming during the extrusion of films

This process has no by-products, the amount of biodegradable plastics formulating the blend produce the same quantity of blend.

Figure 18 shows the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 18: PFC of DEMOs 6 and 8

Table 14: List of equipment DEMO 6 and 8

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Gravimetric Feeding System	Dosing the biodegradable resins in the mixer	1
Banbury mixer	Preparation of the biodegradable blends	2
Conveyor	Transport of the biodegradable blend from the mixer to the extruder	3
Extruder	Blend granulation	4

9.1.2 Scaling factors

Demonstrators 6 and 8 have been already developed at industrial level, the equipment used have a production capacity 30-36 Kg/h, allowing for the production of 500 Kg in a two-shift workday.

- Mandatory material drying, both before and after the blending process, to prevent defects such as gel formation or foaming during film extrusion. which requires additional drying equipment for industrial implementation.
- Accurate gravimetric dosing of biodegradable components is essential to ensure blend homogeneity at industrial scale.
- Availability of industrial pelletizing capacity, required to convert the biodegradable blends into pellets suitable for blown film extrusion.

9.2 Description of Final Products Obtained

9.2.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

Product	Composition	Properties
Formulations for packaging (DEMO6)	PHBV-PBAT	Biodegradable in compost, soil and water Tensile strength>25 MPa Tensile strain>450 %
Formulations for agricultural films (DEMO 8)	PHBV- Starch PAT	Biodegradable in compost soil and water Tensile strength>25 MPa Tensile strain>450 %

9.2.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

Demonstrated compatibility with conventional extrusion and conversion lines, used in both the food packaging sector (Eversia) for DEMO 6 and the agricultural film sector (Solplast) for DEMO 8, without requiring major equipment modifications.

Compliance with the technical requirements of the final film, including mechanical strength, sealability, printability, and stability, depending on the end-use.

Regulatory validation, either for food contact applications (in the case of packaging) or compliance with biodegradability standards (for agricultural use).

Product	Composition	Properties
Flexible food packaging 	PHBV-PBAT	Food contact Biodegradable in compost, soil and water Tensile strength >25 MPa Tensile strain >450 %
Formulations for agricultural films (DEMO 8) 	PHBV- Starch PAT	Biodegradable in compost soil and water Tensile strength >25 MPa Tensile strain >450 %

10 DEMONSTRATOR 7 AND 9

10.1 Technology Transfer and Scalability Assessment

10.1.1 Process description

Demonstrators 7 and 9 are located at GWC's industrial facilities in Alhama de Murcia and CETEC's pilot plant. They both involve recycling plastic waste streams from Demonstrator 1, but with different final products.

- **Demonstrator 7:** Focuses on processing non-metallized plastic fractions from Demonstrator 1 for food packaging.
- **Demonstrator 9:** Focuses on recycling agricultural disinfection film waste and incorporating modified aluminium recovered from Demonstrator 1 to create agricultural mulch with enhanced optical properties

- 1 **STEP 1 (DEMO 9 only) Aluminium modification** following the Grafting-to strategy. The purpose of this modification is to make the aluminium compatible with the plastic matrix. This process was scaled up at BOKU facilities, with batch sizes of up to 1 kg.
- 2 **STEP 2 (DEMO 9 only) Al masterbatch preparation:** The modified aluminium is blended with recycled polyethylene (PE) flakes from DEMO 1 using a compounding twin-screw extruder to create a masterbatch. The material is transformed into pellets which can be used by the plastic processing industry (end users) for the manufacturing of agricultural film with especial optical properties.
- 3 **STEP 3 compounding extrusion process** of the non- metallised recycled plastic fraction coming from DEMO 1, in an extruder with a vacuum system and processing capacity of 1000 Kg/h to eliminate volatiles for deep contamination. The material is transformed into pellets which can be used by the plastic processing industry (end users) for the manufacturing of packaging (DEMO 7) or agricultural film (DEMO 9).

This process has no by-products, the amount of recycled plastic and aluminium formulating the blends produce the same quantity of final pellets.

Figure 19 shows the process flow chart (PFC)

Figure 19: PFC of DEMOs 7 and 9

Table 15: List of equipment DEMO 7 and 9

Equipment Name	Function	Step
Reactor with mechanical stirrer and temperature control	Aluminium modification	1
Twin screw extruder with pelletisation system	Preparation of aluminium masterbatch	2

Compounding with high vacuum system and pelletisation system	Recycled non metallised fraction blending and pelletisation	3
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10.1.2 Scaling factors

Demonstrators 7 and 9 can be easily implemented at industrial scale since the equipment used are available at industrial production capacity.

Key aspects to consider in the Scaling-Up of Demonstrators 7 and 9:

- Extrusion parameters must be tailored to the specific material mix to ensure process stability and product quality.
- Access to relatively homogeneous multilayer agricultural film waste (disinfection film), free of aluminium and without the need for layer separation, which simplifies the recycling process and enhances scalability.
- The material must be clean and dry prior to extrusion, to prevent downstream issues such as gel formation, moisture retention, or gas release.
- Prior aluminium modification process for the production of the masterbatch.
- Proven performance of the modified aluminium as a functional additive.
- Industrial compounding capacity using twin-screw extrusion equipment is required.
- Cooling and pelletizing systems must ensure the stability and quality of the masterbatch, making it suitable for subsequent film extrusion (validated by end-user Solplast).
- The final product functionality must be confirmed, particularly in terms of infrared (IR) barrier optical properties.

10.2 Description of Final Products Obtained

10.2.1 Technical Specifications of Each Product

PRODUCT	COMPOSITION	Characteristics
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Modified aluminium	>95% Al	Food contact grade
LDPE-EVOH-PA recycled pellets	LDPE>95%	Tensile strength > 19 MPa Tensile strain >200% Food contact grade
LDPE recycled pellets		Extrusion grade
LDPE-Al recycled masterbatch pellets	>10% Aluminium	Extrusion grade Food contact grade

10.2.2 Potential Applications and Market Viability

Product	Composition	Properties
Recycled agricultural films with optical properties	0,5% Masterbatch Al + 99,5 % recycled plastic pellets	Tensile strength > 19 MPa Tensile strain >200% Barrier to IR light, cooling effect Validated by end user (Solplast)
Flexible packaging made of recycled plastic	100% recycled plastic pellets	Tensile strength > 19 MPa Tensile strain >200% Validated by end user (Eversia, Citromil, Almond, Mocitos)

BENEFITS

Packaging

- Plastic tax reduction.
- Recycling and Sustainability: Reduces plastic waste and less use of virgin materials.

Agricultural film:

- Soil Solarization: Improves thermal efficiency, increasing soil temperature to eliminate pathogens.
- Weed Control: Efficient light blocking, inhibiting weed growth without chemicals.
- Moisture Retention Improvement: Retains moisture in the soil, reducing the need for frequent irrigation.
- -Erosion Protection: Greater resistance to wear and soil erosion due to increased durability.
- Light Reflection for Crops: Enhances crop growth by reflecting sunlight.
- Chemical-Free Disinfection: Uses natural heat to eliminate pests and pathogens without chemicals.
- Recycling and Sustainability: Reduces plastic waste and less use of virgin materials.
- Increased Lifespan: Improved UV resistance, increasing the durability of the film.
- Greenhouse Crops: Controls temperature and light, promoting plant growth in greenhouses.
- Frost Protection: Reflects heat to maintain higher temperatures during the night.

11 DEMONSTRATOR 10

11.1 Demo 10

In alignment with DoA and Task 6.3 - *Setting the basis for future industrial implementation*, Demo 10 consists of a central digital component aimed to support demos traceability and future industrial scalability. Moreover, it serves as knowledge preservation for being able to digitalize a complex circular economy system.

Aligned with the ambitions of the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the upcoming Digital Product Passport Regulation, the DIS provides a scalable and transparent digital backbone that enables not only the consolidation and verification of project results, but also their transferability to real industrial environments.

The presented work on this document complements the work carried out in deliverables D1.10 – *Data Integration System BETA Version*, which serves as a user guide for the A2C Data Integration System online platform, D1.12 - *A2C Data Integration System (Final)*, that covers the development of a platform to digitize the circular processes in which multilayer and organic plastic waste is generated in the agri-food sector and D1.13 - *A2C Data Integration System (Public Summary)*, which explores the challenges that necessitate the development of DIS, the technological solutions embedded within the system, its contribution to the A2C systemic approach, and its versatility for application beyond the project scope.

11.1.1 Architecture and components of the system

The system architecture allows for secure access by different user types (e.g., agrifood waste producers, plastic recyclers, process operators, end-product manufacturers) with role-specific modules and interfaces. This ensures that each actor can upload, consult and validate the data relevant to their specific activity, without compromising the privacy or integrity of the wider value chain. This platform integrates:

- Web-based data management portal, providing traceability, access control and overall functionality.

- A mobile application that enables on-site data entry and QR code and watermark based traceability, both for technical and non-technical users.
- A blockchain infrastructure, based on the IOTA protocol, which secures critical events milestones and prevents data tampering.
- Digital Product Passport (DPP), which enables structured data visualisation and compliance with future EU requirements.
- A Decision Support Tool (DST), which offers descriptive and predictive analytics and supports multi-criteria decision-making.

11.1.2 Data integration and validation protocol

Data from the different demonstrators has been integrated into DIS following a standardized digital protocol that ensures interoperability and consistency across all the platform.

This protocol begins with data capturing either via QR or web interfaces, using structured data forms that reflect the key specific parameter of each process, such as origin of the material, its unique identification, process date...

Each original residue batch is assigned a unique ID which is generated based on the waste manager who is responsible for its recycling, the date when it is produced and a serial number. This ID is linked to the *Documento de Identificación de Residuos*, which is required by the Spanish administration on industrial scale for waste management. [Link 1](#) shows the identification of the waste that was sent from MOCITOS to GWC. [Link 2](#) generates the report for printing and physical signing. Each batch is assigned a unique QR code and internal traceability ID, which connects it to all relevant upstream and downstream activities. The associated data points are stored within the cloud platform and hashed into the IOTA blockchain to ensure immutability and verifiability [Link 4](#) shows the Digital Product Passport of a potential agricultural mulch film traced on Data Integration System.

For example, both LDPE-EVOH-PA pellets and aluminium flakes are included as products in DEMO 10 in order to track feedstock transformation processes into products. [Link 3](#) shows the traceability of a determined plastic lot in the shape of pellets for further manufacturing, like the agricultural mulch shown before. By this way, it is possible to trace front and back every residue, by-product and final product. For example, related to DEMO 2, [Link 5](#) shows

the traceability of the fiber extract obtained from the lemon waste, one of the by-products of the A2C solution. Another example of record as by-product is shown in [Link 7](#), in which the grape extract is characterized and traced for providing the necessary information to formulators.

One example of the formulations are the nutraceutical products, which are also included in DEMO 10. Thanks to all technologies gathered on DIS, it has been able to generate a final Digital Product Passport which identifies each individual bottle with all the traceability and characterization of the containing product. ([Link 8](#)).

See [DEMO 10 video](#) to better understand the physical treatment of data and deliverable 6.2 with the user guide to access the tool.

11.1.3 Maintenance and legacy

It is paramount to remark that the Data Integration System approach has always been to adapt to the A2C solution. As said in D1.12, it is key to understand that A2C solution is a complex system that holds many different technologies and partners, this means that any interest in joining the solution will need software adaptability to gather new requirements.

DIS is currently deployed in a semi-public configuration (e.g. Beta-tested Android mobile app, web dashboard with partner login, public for final products information), the system is designed for post-project continuity. As described in Deliverable D1.10, the platform will be maintained for at least two years beyond project closure, with open access to all public data components and technical documentation.

Furthermore, a technical support structure has been established (see contact in D1.10, Section 3.2), and public users will be able to access selected features, such as DPP verification, via anonymous QR scanning, reinforcing the long-term value and openness of the platform.

To conclude, the integration of all demonstrators, processes, and validation steps into the A2C Data Integration System constitutes a major achievement of Task 6.3, and a significant contribution to the digitalisation of circular economy value chains.

12 Study of the energy consumption of the Demos at an economy of scale

The nine technical demonstrators built in Agro2Circular project involve 10 different processes to be considered for the energy consumption study at an economy of scale, according to the flowchart showed in Figure 20

Figure 20: Flowchart of the relationship between processes and demonstrator

12.1 Methodology

In order to conduct the scale-up study of the energy consumption, a proprietary calculation system was utilized. This method gives a mathematical relation between the energetic OPEX, C_1 , of an industrial process for a reference size, S_1 , (reference input that the process can carry) and the estimated energetic OPEX, C_2 , of the same process but for a different size S_2 (different input). This method, based on the six-tenths rule, has proved reliable as it is widely used in this type of studies, [1-3] including previous analysis conducted by our company in similar reports [4, 5]. The six tenths rule states:

$$C_2 = C_1 \left(\frac{S_2}{S_1} \right)^n$$

Where n is the cost scaling factor, commonly taken as 0,6.

Along this section, different tables that contain the results of the scale-up study will be included. These tables show the input (new size S_2) and the estimated energetic OPEX (C_2). However, this value will be shown as energy consumption (kWh) and as energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg or kWh/L), calculated dividing the energy consumption of the process/Demo by the considered input.

The reference size (S_1) and the energetic OPEX (C_1) are usually taken from D1.9, although there is one process (Demo 1 – Process 4) where these data have been obtained from D6.1 due to the fact that this process was not registered in the time to deliver D1.9.

Regarding section 11.10, a python program was developed in order to improve the calculation system and show a precise scale-up study trend curve. This program applies the six tenths rule to Demos 3 and 5 considering 10.000 scenarios (inputs/output), instead of the three scenarios considered for the scale-up study from sections 11.2 – 11.9.

12.2 Demo 1

Demonstrator 1 contains process 3, process 4 and process 5 (Table 16). Demo 1 runs with an input of 1,200kg so, in order to perform the scale-up study in each process from this Demo, three industrial scale scenarios have been considered: 25.000 kg, 500.000 kg and 2.500.000 kg. It should be taken into account that every energy consumption data for the Demo scale was extracted from D1.9.

Table 16: Description of the processes involved in DEMO 1

PROCESS 3	Multilayer plastic waste preliminary decontamination + optical sorting
PROCESS 4	Multilayer metallised plastic fraction delamination & sorting and aluminium removal and modification

PROCESS 5	PE/PET plastic fraction pretreatment + enzymatic degradation
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12.2.1 Demonstrator 1. Process 3

Process 3 is made of 2 subprocesses: pre-treatment and optical sorting.

For the **pre-treatment process**, both electricity and natural gas have been used, therefore, energy consumption is divided into electricity energy consumption and natural gas energy consumption.

From D1.9, it is known that pre-treatment consumes 2.880kWh from electricity and 27,72 kWh from natural gas. The energy consumption per input unit is 2,40 kWh/kg and 0,02 kWh/kg respectively.

Applying the six tenths method, the following results were obtained:

Table 17 Demonstrator 1 (process 3). Energy consumption scale-up for pre-treatment

	Process 3: Energy consumption scale-up (pre-treatment)			
	Electricity		Natural gas	
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	17.809,34 kWh	0,71 kWh/kg	171,41 kWh	6,86 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg
500.000 kg	107.464,68 kWh	0,21 kWh/kg	1.034,35 kWh	2,07 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	282.258,97 kWh	0,11 kWh/kg	2.716,74 kWh	1,09 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg

As in can be observed, this part of the process 3 requires much more electricity energy than natural gas energy and as the process input scale goes to higher inputs, the energy required

in the form of natural gas decreases down to $1,09 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg (for an input of 2.500.000 kg).

After the pre-treatment, an **optical sorting** process begins, resulting in an energy consumption of 264 kWh (0,22 kWh/kg per input unit). Scaling-up these data leads to:

Table 18 Demonstrator 1 (process 3). Energy consumption scale-up for optical sorting

Process 3: Energy consumption scale-up (fermentation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	1.632,52 kWh	0,07 kWh/kg
500.000 kg	9.850,93 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	25.873,74 kWh	0,01 kWh/kg

Then, the **total** energy consumption of process 3 is 3.144kWh using electricity and 27,72 kWh using natural gas (2,62 kWh/kg and 0,02kWh/kg respectively). The scale-up study provides the following results:

Table 19 Demonstrator 1 (process 3). Energy consumption scale-up.

Process 3: Energy consumption scale-up (total)				
Product input scale-up	Electricity		Natural gas	
	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	19.441,86 kWh	0,78 kWh/kg	171,41 kWh	$6,86 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
500.000 kg	117.315,61 kWh	0,23 kWh/kg	1.034,35 kWh	$2,07 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg

2.500.000 kg	308.132,70 kWh	0,12 kWh/kg	2.716,74 kWh	1,09 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg
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Along this section, it will be demonstrated that the scale-up study will lead to a decreasing energy consumption per input unit behaviour (besides the logical increase of the energy consumption in kWh), so the larger the input of the process is, the lower the energetic cost per input unit will be. This is illustrated by the previous table, where the energy consumption per input unit of process 3 for a 1.200 kg input (Demo scale) is 2,62 kWh (natural gas not included), while for a 2,5 million kg input (industrial scale) is 0,12 kWh/kg.

12.2.2 Demonstrator 1. Process 4

The scale-up study of process 4 has been conducted by considering real data obtained from D6.2.

Process 4 is made of just one subprocess: delamination and sorting. This subprocess consumes over 31,18 kWh for an input of 5,8 kg. Then, the energy consumption per input unit is 5,38 kWh/kg.

The six tenths rule was applied for the same three scenarios as those chosen in process 3 but adding one more scenario, 1.200 kg, whose objective is to give a total energy consumption for the entire Demo.

Then, the following results are obtained:

Table 20 Demonstrator 1 (process 4). Energy consumption scale-up.

Product input scale-up	Process 4: Energy consumption scale-up	
	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.200 kg	764,41 kWh	0,64 kWh/kg
25.000 kg	4.726,98 kWh	0,19 kWh/kg
500.000 kg	28.523,40 kWh	0,06 kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	74.917,51 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

12.2.3 Demonstrator 1. Process 5

Process 5 consists of 3 subprocesses: PET/PE pre-treatment, PET/PE enzymatic degradation and MHET conversion. This process runs just with electrical power.

PET/PE pretreatment consumes 6,20 kWh for the Demo input, meaning that the energy consumption per input unit for this part of the process 5 is $5,17 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg. Attending to the previous processes, this value is expected to decrease as the scale-up study goes on, leading to a very low energy consumption per input unit for an industrial scale input:

Table 21 Demonstrator 1 (process 5). Energy consumption scale-up for PET/PE pre-treatment

Process 5: Energy consumption scale-up (PET / PE pre-treatment)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	38,34 kWh	$1,53 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
500.000 kg	231,35 kWh	$4,63 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	607,64 kWh	$2,43 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg

PET/PE enzymatic degradation process has an energy consumption of 24 kWh (0,02kWh/kg). The scale-up study was conducted, giving the following results:

Table 22 Demonstrator 1 (process 5). Energy consumption scale-up for PET/PE enzymatic degradation.

Process 5: Energy consumption scale-up (PET/PE enzymatic degradation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	148,41 kWh	$5,93 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg

500.000 kg	895,54 kWh	$1,79 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	2.352,16 kWh	$9,41 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg

The energy consumption for the Demo scale input of the **MHET conversion** is 1,5. The energy consumption per input unit is $1,25 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg. Therefore, the six tenths method results in the following:

Table 23 Demonstrator 1 (process 5). Energy consumption scale-up for MHET conversion.

Process 5: Energy consumption scale-up (MHET conversion)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	9,28 kWh	$3,71 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg
500.000 kg	55,97 kWh	$1,12 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	147,01 kWh	$5,88 \times 10^{-5}$ kWh/kg

The **entire process 5** consumes a total of 31,70 kWh, that is, 0,03 kWh/kg. As said before, this is not high, so it is expected to reach a lower energy consumption per input unit to run the entire process as the input for the process increases. The following data show this result:

Table 24 Demonstrator 1 (process 5). Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 1 (process 5): Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	196,03 kWh	$7,84 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
500.000 kg	1182,86 kWh	$2,37 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg

2.500.000 kg

3.106,81 kWh

1,24 x 10⁻³ kWh/kg

Running the entire process 5 for an input of 2,5 million kg (industrial scale) consumes 1,24 x 10⁻³ kWh/kg approximately, compared to the 0,02 kWh/kg required at Demo scale.

12.2.4 Demonstrator 1. Total

The total energy consumption of Demo 1 for an input of 1.200 kg is 3.967,83 kWh (3,31 kWh/kg). Scaling-up these results leads to the following table:

Table 25 Demonstrator 1. Energy consumption scale-up.

Product input scale-up	Demo 1: Energy consumption scale-up (total)	
	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
25.000 kg	24.536,28 kWh	0,98 kWh/kg
500.000 kg	148.056,21 kWh	0,30 kWh/kg
2.500.000 kg	388.873,76 kWh	0,16 kWh/kg

This table show the expected trend mentioned before. The energy consumption per input unit of Demo 1 decreases as the input for this Demo increases. As said, this behaviour will be a general trend along every section from now on.

12.3 Demo 2

Demonstrator 2 leads process 8 (Table 26), which is divided into three parts depending on its input: EG, TPA or lemon. However, there is no data from process 8 for TPA, so it is not included here.

As EG input is different (higher) from lemon input, different scale-up scenarios have been decided. Those scenarios will be exposed in their corresponding section.

Table 26: Description of the process involved in DEMO 2

PROCESS 8	Bioconversion of EG into GA Bioconversion of TPA into PCA Bioproduction of microbial oils with lemon waste as the carbon source
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12.3.1 Demonstrator 2. Process 8 (input: EG)

In order to process EG, there are two subprocesses: Biomass & GA production and DWP: centrifugation.

The input for this process at Demo scale is approximately 731,04 L. Then, the scale-up study was conducted for three scenarios: 10.000 L, 100.000 L and 1 million L.

The energy consumption for **biomass & GA production** is 50,51 kWh. That means that the energy consumption per input unit is 0,07 kWh/L. By applying the six tenths method to the previously mentioned scale-up scenarios, the following results were obtained:

Table 27 Demonstrator 2 (process 8, EG). Energy consumption scale-up for Biomass & GA production.

Demo 2 (process 8, EG): Energy consumption scale-up (Biomass & GA production)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
10.000 L	242,66 kWh	0,02 kWh/L
100.000 L	966,04 kWh	9,66 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/L
1 million L	3.845,88 kWh	3,85 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/L

For the **DWP: centrifugation**, the energy consumption is 2,60 kWh ($3,56 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/L). Scaling-up this process gives the next results:

Table 28 Demonstrator 2 (process 8, EG). Energy consumption scale-up for DWP: centrifugation

Demo 2 (process 8, EG): Energy consumption scale-up (DWP: centrifugation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
10.000 L	12,49 kWh	$1,25 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/L
100.000 L	49,73 kWh	$4,97 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/L
1 million L	197,97 kWh	$1,98 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/L

The **total** energy consumption for the process 8 (input: EG) is 255,15 kWh and its energy consumption per input unit is 0,07 kWh/L. The next table indicates these parameters scaled-up to industrial scales:

Table 29 Demonstrator 2 (process 8, EG). Energy consumption scale-up.

Demo 2 (process 8, EG): Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
10.000 L	242,66 kWh	0,02 kWh/L
100.000 L	966,04 kWh	$2,37 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/L
1 million L	3.845,88 kWh	$1,24 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/L

These data show the expected behaviour, passing from those 0,07 kWh/L for a 731,04 L input to the $1,24 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/L required for 1 million L input.

12.3.2 Demonstrator 2. Process 8 (input: lemon)

This part of process 8 runs with lemon as the main input and is composed of 4 subprocesses: Yeast fermentation, DWP: centrifugation, DWP: extraction and solvent evaporation. Regarding DWP: centrifugation, the energy consumption is meaningful, so it is not taken into account.

The initial input for this part of the process is 1,53 L, so the scale-up study will consider an input of 50 L, 1.000 L and 100.000 L.

For the **yeast fermentation**, the energy consumption is 21,70 kWh and its energy consumption per input unit is 14,22 kWh/L. Calculations were elaborated following the six tenths method and these results were obtained:

Table 30 . Demonstrator 2 (process 8, lemon). Energy consumption scale-up for yeast fermentation

Demo 2 (process 8, lemon): Energy consumption scale-up (Yeast fermentation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
50 L	176,12 kWh	3,52 kWh/L
1.000 L	1.062,73 kWh	1,06 kWh/L
100.000 L	16.843,18 kWh	0,17 kWh/L

DWP: extraction consumes 13,44 kWh, that is, 8,81 kWh/L for the Demo input scale. Therefore, the scale-up study results in the following:

Table 31 Demonstrator 2 (process 8, lemon). Energy consumption scale-up for DWP: extraction

Demo 2 (process 8, lemon): Energy consumption scale-up (DWP: extraction)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
50 L	176,12 kWh	3,52 kWh/L
1.000 L	1.062,73 kWh	1,06 kWh/L
100.000 L	16.843,18 kWh	0,17 kWh/L

The energetic cost of the **solvent evaporation** subprocess is 9,28 kWh (at Demo scale), and its energetic cost per input unit is 6,08 kWh/L. Changing the input scale to industrial scale inputs leads to:

Table 32 Demonstrator 2 (process 8, lemon). Energy consumption scale-up for solvent evaporation

Demo 2 (process 8, lemon): Energy consumption scale-up (solvent evaporation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
50 L	75,30 kWh	1,51 kWh/L
1.000 L	454,38 kWh	0,45 kWh/L
100.000 L	7.201,37 kWh	0,07 kWh/L

12.3.3 Demonstrator 2. Total

The total energy consumption of process 8 (input: lemon) is 44,42 kWh (29,11 kWh/L). The energetic cost of this process for the different scale-up inputs proposed is:

Table 33 . Demonstrator 2 (process 8, lemon). Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 2 (process 8, lemon): Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/L)
50 L	360,48 kWh	7,20 kWh/L
1.000 L	2.175,17 kWh	2,18 kWh/L
100.000 L	34.474,13 kWh	0,34 kWh/L

12.4 Demo 3

Demo 3 yield processes 1 and 2, both with different subprocesses (Table 34). Even though the energy consumption data for process 2 is calculated by considering a 40 kg input (process 1 works with 50 kg of input), the scale-up study was conducted for 50 kg, assuming there is no significant change between the energy consumption for each input. This allows us to calculate a total energy consumption scale-up for the entire Demo.

That being said, the considered scenarios are: 1.000 kg, 10.000 kg and 100.000 kg.

Table 34: Description of the process involved in DEMO 3

PROCESS 1	Fruit & vegetable waste pretreatment Enzymatic polyphenols and fibre extraction Separation of liquid and solid fractions
PROCESS 2	Fibre purification and dehydration Polyphenols purification and lyophilisation

12.4.1 Demonstrator 3. Process 1

Process 1 consists of three different subprocesses: Pre-treatment, enzymatic extraction + filtration and purification.

For the **pre-treatment**, energy consumption is 1 kWh, which divided by 50 kg (Demo input) gives an energy consumption per input unit of 0,02 kWh/kg. Then, for the scenarios mentioned before, the following data have been calculated:

Table 35 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for pre-treatment

Demo 3 (process 1): Energy consumption scale-up (pre-treatment)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	6,03 kWh	$6,03 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
10.000 kg	24,02 kWh	$2,40 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
100.000 kg	95,64 kWh	$9,64 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg

Regarding the **Enzymatic extraction + filtration** subprocess, energy consumption is again divided into electricity and natural gas (as in Demo 1). This part of process 1 consumes 93,06 kWh at Demo scale, being 1kWh (0.02 kWh/kg) when using electricity and the other 92,06 kWh (1,84 kWh/kg) when using natural gas. The scale-up study results in the following:

Table 36 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for enzymatic extraction + filtration.

Process 1: Energy consumption scale-up (Enzymatic extraction + filtration)				
		Electricity		Natural gas
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	6,03 kWh	$6,03 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg	555,48 kWh	0,56 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	24,02 kWh	$2,40 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg	2.211,39 kWh	0,22 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	95,64 kWh	$9,64 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg	8.803,72 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg

Finally, for the **purification** part, energy consumption is 37,12 kWh, so its energy consumption per input unit is 0,74 kWh/kg. Applying the six tenths method, the following data is obtained:

Table 37 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for purification

Demo 3 (process 1): Energy consumption scale-up (purification)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	223,99 kWh	0,22 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	891,72 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.549,98 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg

This **entire process** consumes 39,12 kWh (Demo scale) when using electricity and 92,06 kWh when using natural gas. The total energy consumption per input unit using electricity and natural gas is 0,78 kWh/kg and 1,84 kWh/kg respectively. The next table shows the scale-up study results for process 1:

Table 38 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up

Process 1: Energy consumption scale-up (total)				
		Electricity		Natural gas
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	236,06 kWh	0,24 kWh/kg	555,48 kWh	0,56 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	939,76 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg	2.211,39 kWh	0,22 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3741,25 kWh	0,04kWh/kg	8.803,72 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg

Both, electricity and natural gas energy consumption per input unit present the same trend, as seen in Demo 1.

12.4.2 Demonstrator 3. Process 2

In process 2, there are two subprocesses: Dehydration (solid phase) and Lyophilisation (liquid phase).

Dehydration consumes a total of 38,40 kWh, meaning that the energy consumption per input unit is 0,77 kWh/kg. The scale-up study provides these results:

Table 39 Demonstrator 3 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for dehydration (solid phase)

Demo 3 (process 2): Energy consumption scale-up (dehydration (solid phase))		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	231,71 kWh	0,23 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	922,46 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.672,39 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg

On the other hand, Lyophilisation consumes 240 kWh (4,80 kWh/kg). The six tenths method leads to these data:

Table 40 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for lyophilisation (liquid phase)

Demo 3 (process 2): Energy consumption scale-up (Lyophilisation (solid phase))		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	1.448,20 kWh	1,45 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	5.765,40 kWh	0,58 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	22.952,46 kWh	0,23 kWh/kg

Energy consumption for process 2 is 278,40 kWh and its energy consumption per input unit is 5,57 kWh/kg for the Demo scale. Therefore, scaling-up of these data gives:

Table 41 Demonstrator 3 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 3 (process 2): Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	1.679,92 kWh	1,68 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	6.687,86 kWh	0,67 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	26.624,85 kWh	0,27 kWh/kg

12.4.3 Demonstrator 3. Total

With both process 1 and process 2 scaled-up, it is possible to give an estimation of the energy consumption for the entire process for each scenario of the scale-up study.

Adding the total energy consumption of process 1 and process 2 (and their energy consumption per input unit) for the 50 kg of input (Demo scale) gives 409,58 kWh (8,19 kWh/kg). Applying the six tenths method to these results will lead to the following data:

Table 42 Demonstrator 3 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for purification

Demo 3: Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	2.471,45 kWh	2,47 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	9.839,01 kWh	0,98 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	39.169,81 kWh	0,39 kWh/kg

12.5 Demo 4

Demonstrator 4 also yields processes 1 and 2, being their subprocesses slightly different (Table 45).

This Demo currently runs for an input of 100 kg, so the scale-up study will aim to calculate the energy consumption of Demo 4 with an input of 1.000 kg, 10.000kg and 100.000 kg.

Table 43: Description of the process involved in DEMO 4

PROCESS 1	Fruit & vegetable waste pretreatment Enzymatic polyphenols and fibre extraction Separation of liquid and solid fractions
PROCESS 2	Polyphenols MAE extraction, purification and dehydration Fibre purification and dehydration

12.5.1 Demonstrator 4. Process 1

Process 1 in Demo 4 consists of three subprocesses: pre-treatment, enzymatic extraction and centrifugation. Centrifugation, however, could be omitted but is included in this study in order to achieve a complete view of the demonstrator.

Pre-treatment consumes over 0,28 kWh ($2,83 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg). Thus, scaling-up these data will give:

Table 44 Demonstrator 4 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for Pre-treatment.

Demo 4 (process 1): Energy consumption scale-up (pre- treatment)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)

1.000 kg	1,13 kWh	$1,13 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
10.000 kg	4,49 kWh	$4,49 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg
100.000 kg	17,88 kWh	$1,79 \times 10^{-4}$ kWh/kg

Energy consumption for **enzymatic extraction** is 3,00 kWh, resulting in a 0,03 kWh/kg energy consumption per input unit. Increasing the amount of input result in the following data:

Table 45 . Demonstrator 4 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for enzymatic extraction.

Demo 4 (process 1): Energy consumption scale-up (enzymatic extraction)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	11,94 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	47,55 kWh	$4,75 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
100.000 kg	189,29 kWh	$1,89 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg

After the enzymatic extraction, the centrifugation process takes place, consuming over 20,00 kWh (0,20 kWh/kg) at Demo scale. Changing the scale, from Demo scale to industrial scale, results in:

Table 46 Demonstrator 4 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up for centrifugation.

Demo 4 (process 1): Energy consumption scale-up
(centrifugation)

Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	79,62 kWh	0,07 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	316,98 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	1.261,91 kWh	0,01 kWh/kg

By looking at these tables it is possible to estimate the total energy consumption of the process 1 for industrial scales. Knowing that the entire process consumes over 23,28 kWh (0,24 kWh/kg), the following is estimated:

Table 47 Demonstrator 4 (process 1). Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 4 (process 1) :Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	92,69 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	369,02 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	1.469,08 kWh	0,01 kWh/kg

12.5.2 Demonstrator 4. Process 2

In demonstrator 4, process 2 differs depending on the process input: solid phase or liquid phase. However, the scale-up study was elaborated considering the same three scenarios from process 1 for both phases.

12.5.2.1 Solid phase:

The solid phase input undergoes two subprocesses: Microwave extraction (MAE) and purification + concentration.

Microwave extraction can only run for an input of 10 kg, so it has to run 10 times for the 100 kg of input from the Demo to work. Therefore, it consumes 33,33 kWh, resulting in a 0,33kWh/kg energy consumption per input unit. The scale-up study for this part of process 2 causes the following:

Table 48 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for microwave extraction.

Demo 4 (process2, solid phase): Energy consumption scale-up (Microwave extraction)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	132,70 kWh	0,13 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	528,30 kWh	0,05 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	2.103,19 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg

The purification + concentration process consumes 2,50 kWh (over 0,03 kWh/kg). When applying the six tenths method, the following data are obtained:

Table 49 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for microwave extraction.

Demo 4 (process 2, solid phase): Energy consumption scale-up (purification + concentration)

Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	9,95 kWh	0,01 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	39,62 kWh	$3,96 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg
100.000 kg	157,74 kWh	$1,58 \times 10^{-3}$ kWh/kg

The entire process 2 for the solid phase input consumes 35,83 kWh (0,36 kWh/kg). Then, the scale up study sparks the following results:

Table 50 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up (total)

Demo 4 (process2, solid phase): Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kW/kg)
1.000 kg	142,66 kWh	0,14 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	567,92 kWh	0,06 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	2.260,93 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg

12.5.2.2 Liquid phase

The liquid phase also has two subprocesses: Ultrafiltration and dehydration.

The **ultrafiltration** subprocess consumes over 7,50 kWh (0,08 kWh/kg). The scale-up study leads to:

Table 51 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for ultrafiltration

Demo 4 (process2, liquid phase): Energy consumption scale-up (Ultrafiltration)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	29,86 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	118,87 kWh	0,01 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	473,22 kWh	4,73 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg

Dehydration subprocess has an energy consumption of 48,00 kWh, that is, 0,48 kWh/kg. Scaling-up these data leads to:

Table 52 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for purification + concentration

Demo 4 (process2, liquid phase):Energy consumption scale-up (Dehydration)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	191,09 kWh	0,19 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	760,75 kWh	0,08 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.028,60 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

Finally, **the entire process 2 for the liquid phase input** consumes 55,50 kWh (0,56 kWh/kg). Then:

Table 53 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 4 (process2, liquid phase):Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	220,95 kWh	0,22 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	879,62 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.501,81 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg

12.5.2.3 Total energy consumption for process 2

By adding the data from the previous sections, the energy consumption at Demo scale (100 kg input) is 91,33 kWh, causing an energy consumption per input unit of 0,91 kWh/kg. Raising the input to industrial scale results in:

Table 54 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for purification + concentration

Demo 4 (process 2): Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	158,27 kWh	0,16 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	630,08 kWh	0,06 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	2.508,38 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

12.5.3 Demonstrator 4. Total

Demonstrator 4 consumes over 114,62 kWh (1,15 kWh/kg) at Demo scale. The scale-up study was conducted for this Demo, obtaining:

Table 55 Demonstrator 4 (process 2). Energy consumption scale-up for purification+concentration

Demo 4: Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
1.000 kg	250,96 kWh	0,25 kWh/kg
10.000 kg	999,09 kWh	0,10 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.977,46 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg

This table shows the expected trend.

12.6 Demo 5

Demo 5 consists of process 9 (Table 56), which is divided into 4 parts: fermentation, filtration, drying and PHBV extraction + purification. Process 9 uses liquid lemon extract produced in Demo 3, but the energetic cost for its production was taken into account in that demonstrator so it is not included here.

Table 56: Description of the process involved in DEMO 5

PROCESS 9	Fermentation of PHBV reach biomass, Biomass filtration Biomass drying PHBV extraction + purification
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At the Demo scale, this process can run a 53,15 kg input, so the scale-up study to industrial scale inputs was elaborated for 1000 kg, 10.000 kg and for 100.000 kg.

The fermentation process consumes 654,32 kWh (12,31 kWh/kg for the Demo scale input). Scale-up study for this part of process 9 yields the following results:

Table 57 Demonstrator 5. Energy consumption scale-up for fermentation).

Demo 5: Energy consumption scale-up (fermentation)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	3.806,17 kWh	3,81 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	15.152,64 kWh	1,52 kWh/kg
1 million kg	60.323,74 kWh	0,60 kWh/kg

Fermentation outputs go to a **filtration process** whose energy consumption is 36 kWh, resulting in a 0,68 kWh/kg consumption per input unit (53,15 kg). The six tenths method reaches these results:

Table 58 Demonstrator 5. Energy consumption scale-up for filtration.

Demo 5: Energy consumption scale-up (filtration)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	209,41 kWh	0,21 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	833,68 kWh	0,08 kWh/kg
1 million kg	3.318,95 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

The energy consumption for the drying process is 129,60 kWh and its energy consumption per input unit is 2,44 kWh/kg. The scale-up for this part of process 9 causes the following:

Table 59 Demonstrator 5. Energy consumption scale-up for drying.

Demo 5: Energy consumption scale-up (drying)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	753,88 kWh	0,75 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	3.001,26 kWh	0,30 kWh/kg
1 million kg	11.948,22 kWh	0,12 kWh/kg

PHBV extraction and purification consume 8,25 kWh for the Demo scale, that is, 0,16 kWh/kg per input unit. By scaling-up these data, the results obtained are:

Table 60 . Demonstrator 5. Energy consumption scale-up for PHBV extraction and purification

Demo 5: Energy consumption scale-up (PHBV extraction and purification)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	47,99 kWh	0,05 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	191,05 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg
1 million kg	760,59 kWh	7,61 x 10 ⁻³ kWh/kg

The **entire process 9** gives an energy consumption of 4.817,45 kWh (15,58 kWh/kg). The scale-up study for the entire Demo 5 yields:

Table 61 Demonstrator 5. Energy consumption scale-up for PHBV extraction and purification

Demo 5: Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	4.817,45 kWh	4,82 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	19.178,63 kWh	1,92 kWh/kg
1 million kg	76.351,49 kWh	0,76 kWh/kg

Scaling-up process 9 from Demo scale to an industrial scale means lowering the energy consumption per input unit, going from 15,58 kWh/kg for an input of 53,15kg (Demo scale) to 0,76kWh/kg for an input of 100.000 kg (industrial scale). The same applies for each one of the subprocesses that process 9 is conformed to individually, as the data tables for these subprocesses show.

12.7 Demo 6 + 8

Demonstrators 6 and 8 are in charge of process 10 (Table 67). This process consumes 224 kWh for an input of 518 kg, then, the total energy consumption per input unit is 0,43 kWh/kg. Since the input for the Demo scale (518 kg) is known, the scale-up calculations were elaborated for an input of 10.000kg, 100.000kg and for 1 million kg (industrial scale).

Table 62: Description of the process involved in DEMOs 6 and 8

PROCESS 10	Preparation of the biodegradable compounds
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Table 63 Demonstrator 6 + 8. Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 6 + 8: Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	1.323,28 kWh	0,13 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	5.268,05 kWh	0,05 kWh/kg
1 million kg	20.972,50 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg

12.8 Demo 7

Demo 7 holds process 6 (Table 70). Aluminium modification (process 4) is included in Demo 1, therefore, it has not been considered in this Demo. Process 6 consists of 4 subprocesses (Multilayer treatment, Extrusion + compatibilization and transformation) and runs for a 531 kg input.

In order to perform the scale-up study, three industry scale scenarios according to its input have been considered: 10.000kg, 100.000kg and 1million kg.

Table 64: Description of the process involved in DEMO 7

PROCESS 6	<p>Non-metallised plastic fraction vacuum decontamination (multilayer treatment)</p> <p>Compatibilization and extrusion</p> <p>Material transformation into plastic films</p>
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First, process 6 starts with the **multilayer treatment**. It consumes 182,21 kWh (for the previously mentioned input), which means that the energy consumption per input unit for the multilayer treatment is 0,34 kWh/kg. Taking that data into account and applying the six tenths method, the scale-up study results in the following:

Table 65 Demonstrator 7. Energy consumption scale-up for the multilayer treatment.

Demo 7: Energy consumption scale-up (Multilayer treatment)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	1.060,51 kWh	0,11 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	4.221,97 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg
1 million kg	16,807,97 kWh	0,02 kWh/kg

Then, the **extrusion + compatibilisation** process takes place, consuming 380 kWh, that is, 0,70 kWh/kg. For this subprocess, the scale-up study leads to the following results:

Table 66 Demonstrator 7. Energy consumption scale-up for Extrusion + compatibilisation.

Demo 7: Energy consumption scale-up (extrusion + compatibilization)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	2.211,70 kWh	0,22 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	8.804,95 kWh	0,09 kWh/kg
1 million kg	35.053,14 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

Finally, for the **transformation** process, the energy consumption is 1.225,50 kWh (2,27 kWh/kg). By scaling-up these data, the results obtained are:

Table 67 Demonstrator 7. Energy consumption scale-up for transformation

Demo 7: Energy consumption scale-up (transformation)		
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Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	7.132,74 kWh	0,71 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	28.395,96 kWh	0,28 kWh/kg
1 million kg	113.046,37 kWh	0,11 kWh/kg

The total energy consumption for the entire process 6 is 1.787,71 kWh, which causes an energy consumption per input unit of 3,31 kWh/kg. By scaling-up those results, we obtain:

Table 68 Demonstrator 7. Energy consumption scale-up (total).

Demo 7: Energy consumption scale-up (total)		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	10.404,96 kWh	1,04 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	41.422,89 kWh	0,04 kWh/kg
1 million kg	164.907,48 kWh	0,16 kWh/kg

Once again, the energy consumption per input unit decreases as the input for the process increases (that is an immediate result from the previous data regarding the subprocesses from this Demo) from 3,31 kWh/kg for the Demo scale to 0,16kWh/kg for an input of 1 million kg.

12.9 Demo 9

Demonstrator 9 just runs process 7 (Table 69). The multilayer treatment is not taken into account for this demonstrator as it was included in Demo 7. Aluminium modification (process 4) is included in Demo 1, therefore, it has not been considered in this Demo.

Table 69: Description of the process involved in DEMO 7

PROCESS 7	Multilayer agro plastic waste compatibilization and extrusion Material transformation into plastic films
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From D1.9 we know that the energy consumption of this Demo, considering an 875kg of input, is 459,4 kWh, so the energy consumption per input unit at Demo scale is 0.525 kWh/kg.

The scale-up scenarios considered to perform the study are the same as for Demo 7. The calculations were elaborated following the Six tenths method, reaching the following results:

Table 70 Demonstrator 9. Energy consumption scale-up

Demo 9: Energy consumption scale-up		
Product input scale-up	Energy consumption (kWh)	Energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg)
10.000 kg	2.006,22 kWh	0,20 kWh/kg
100.000 kg	7.986,91 kWh	0,08 kWh/kg
1 million kg	31.796,47 kWh	0,03 kWh/kg

As it can be observed, total energy consumption increases as the scale-up takes place, increasing from 459,4 kWh for an 875 kg input to 31.796,5 kWh, but energy consumption per input unit decreases considerably (as said in Demo 1), being 0,2 kWh/kg for the first scenario (10 T), 0,08 for 100 T and 0,03 for the last scale-up scenario (1 million kg).

12.10 General trends analysis

Every Demo (and thus, every process from each one) presents the expected trend stated in the analysis of Demo 1: the energetic OPEX for a Demo/process, considering energy consumption per input unit (kWh/kg or kWh/L), decreases as its input increases.

To illustrate this behaviour, a detailed study was conducted for Demos 3 and 5.

In the previous sections, the scale-up study for every Demo was completed considering three different scenarios according to Demo input. The data extracted from those scenarios, although they allow us to discern the mentioned trend, are not enough if the trend curve wants to be observed.

Therefore, a short Python program was developed to enhance the six tenths-based calculation method. This program was applied to multiple scenarios as needed to accurately depict the trend curve. The curve was obtained from the fitting of 10,000 scaling values (as opposed to 3, as in the previous sections), with the aim of conducting a much more in-depth study and obtaining an accurate curve for energy optimization in economies of scale.

12.10.1 Demo 5

Figure 21: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 5. Evolution of energy consumption per material input.

As it can be observed, for Demo 5 the energy consumption per input unit exponentially decreases as the input increases. Let us take a closer look to better observe the curve:

Figure 22: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 5. Evolution of energy consumption per material input at a closer scale

12.10.2 Demo 3

For this detailed study of Demo 3, the energetic OPEX per both input and output was taken into account. That is, the six tenths method was applied for the energy consumption per input unit of the Demo for its input (50 kg) and also to the energy consumption per output unit.

Attending to the energetic OPEX per input unit, the trend curve is:

Figure 23: Figure 21: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 3. Evolution of energy consumption per material input.

Taking a closer look:

Figure 24: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 3. Evolution of energy consumption per material input at closer scale

On the other hand, the outputs that belong to Demo 3 are fiber extract (3,6 kg) and phenolic extract (0,6 kg), for an initial input of 50 kg. The energy consumption per output unit of Demo 3 is 47,10 kWh/kg and 618,63 kWh/kg respectively.

The scale-up trend for the fiber extract is represented in the following graphic:

Figure 25: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 3. Evolution of energy consumption per material input.

And the curve for the phenolic extract is:

Figure 26: Scale up trend curve for DEMO 3. Evolution of energy consumption per material input at a closer scale.

Both of these curves and those referred to the Demo 3 input show, once again, the expected shape. This trend implies a saving in energy consumption per input unit as the process running is loaded with higher inputs (therefore, producing more outputs), so scaling-up the Demos to industrial scale would be beneficial in terms of energy saving, and thus, production cost reduction.

13 Conclusions

The scalability of the different technologies has been demonstrated by the construction of the different demonstrators at pilot scale but some challenges remain for their industrial implementation. This deliverable presents the significant progress made within the framework of the project, highlighting the integration of key technologies and their evaluation in a relevant industrial environment. Throughout the process, we have identified areas for improvement and optimization that will be crucial to ensure the scalability and sustainability of the solution in the long term:

DEMO 1: the performance of the optical sorting highly depends on the feeding speed and size of the plastic fragments yield from the waste washing line. The delamination unit capacity is limited by the bulk density of the plastic to be treated.

DEMO 2: Scaling up the bioconversion of TPA to PCA is a major challenge due to TPA solubility and uptake. The variability in the composition of waste-derived inputs requires prior validation and standardization to ensure process stability and consistent results.

DEMO 3: The main bottleneck identified for this demonstrator is the stabilization stage, specifically the freeze-drying (lyophilization) process, which has a low processing capacity compared to the extraction and purification rates. Lyophilization is also highly energy-intensive. The high variability of raw materials (e.g., in microbiological stability, polyphenol, or fibre content) necessitates a pre-treatment step to homogenize the waste.

DEMO 4: Similar to Demonstrator 3, the purification step using resins is a bottleneck because it requires large quantities of resin and is a time-consuming process. The lyophilization process is also considered a bottleneck due to its high energy consumption. Homogenizing the variable raw materials is another challenge that requires proper pre-treatment

DEMO 5: A significant challenge for scaling up the PHBV extraction process is the need to maintain high-quality biomass with high thermal stability and a low content of unwanted

solids. The reutilisation of salt and water is a mandatory step to ensure the economic and environmental sustainability of the process.

DEMO 6 and 8: The materials must be thoroughly dried both before and after blending to prevent defects like gel formation or foaming during the extrusion of films. Additionally, the final products need regulatory validation for food contact or compliance with biodegradability standards.

DEMO 7 and 9: a key challenge is ensuring the feedstock is clean and dry prior to extrusion to prevent issues downstream, such as moisture retention or gel formation. The extrusion parameters must be specifically tailored to the material mix to ensure stability and quality. For Demonstrator 9, a crucial step is the prior aluminium modification process for creating the masterbatch, and the final product's functionality, specifically its infrared (IR) barrier optical properties.

Results obtained so far are promising and provide a solid foundation for further research, where the different technologies can be refined/optimized to identify new application opportunities across various industries. It is expected that the next steps will continue to contribute to the overall success of the project, consolidating its impact both in the industrial field and in the transition toward a more sustainable model.

This digital system supports the traceability and future industrial scalability of the demonstrators and helps preserve knowledge for digitizing a complex circular economy model. The DIS platform is adaptable to new requirements and will be maintained for at least five years post-project, with open access to public data and technical documentation.

The study on the energy consumption of demonstrators at an economy scale demonstrates that scaling up the A2C demonstrators to an industrial level would be beneficial in terms of energy savings and production cost reduction.

14 Bibliography

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